

ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFECTS OF AIR POLLUTION ON SOCIO-ECONOMIC ACTIVITIES IN PORT HARCOURT, RIVERS STATE NIGERIA.

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Abstract: *This study assessed the effects of air pollution on the socio-economic activities of the inhabitants of Port Harcourt Local Government Area in River State South – South geopolitical zone of Nigeria. The objectives of the research include; to find out the major sources of air pollution in the study area, (ii) to examine the effects of air pollution on the social activities of the inhabitants of Port Harcourt Local Government Area (iii) to explore the effects of air pollution on the economic livelihood of the inhabitants of Port Harcourt Local Government Area (iv) to identify the challenges encountered by business owners, farmers, and other individuals due to air pollution effects in the study area. Four research questions and two hypotheses were postulated to guide the study. Survey research design was adopted for the study. Stratified and purposive sampling techniques were adopted for the study. Both primary and secondary sources of data were used. The population of the study was 1,245,316 inhabitants of Port Harcourt Local Government Area (LGA), and the sample size was 400. Descriptive and inferential statistics particularly multiple regression was used to describe and test the hypotheses. Finding arising from research objective one showed that air pollution in Port Harcourt Local Government Area was as a result of industrial and illegal bunkering activities. Findings arising from research objective three revealed that the residents of the study area were affected in their businesses and social life and perceived air pollution as a source of black soot, in their various residence and business activities. Findings arising from the test of hypotheses showed that there was a significant effect of air pollution on the social activities/ participation of residents in Port Harcourt Local Government Area with an F value of 0.22274895 being greater than 0.05. In the same vein the findings of the second hypothesis are accepted which stated that air pollution had a significant effect on the economic livelihood of the inhabitants of Port Harcourt Local Government Area since the F value of 0.755070323 was greater than the significant level of 0.05. Based on the above findings, it is recommended that government should implement and monitor the compliance of industries and human activities with respect to air pollution policies. It was equally recommended that government should encourage oil and gas companies to recycle and reuse their waste products for other productions so as to reduce the incidence of air pollution in the study area.*

Keywords: Air Pollution, Black soot, Industrial Activities, Farming activities, illegal banking, traffic congestion.

INTRODUCTION

In the past one decade, Port Harcourt City has sporadically witnessed a significant decline in visibility that was hitherto characterized by bright atmosphere. The extreme reduction in visibility has posed difficulty to driving and the movement of aircrafts. Apart from the palpable reduction in visibility, high concentration of soot or carbon particles has equally been observed in different parts of Port Harcourt. The soot usually appears as clouds laden with dark particulate matter on the skyline in various parts of the city. The black soot settles in homes, and makes everywhere appear dirty, even when cleaned thoroughly and regularly (Kalu, 2018). It is visible on window nets, streets, walls, floors and bed sheets, in both private and public places, even on children's feet when innocently playing in an open space. The above presentation suggests a strong evidence of overwhelming air pollution in Port Harcourt city. Air pollution occurs when some gases in the atmosphere exist at higher-than-normal conditions, and can be seriously harmful to human health. Examples of these include: nitrogen oxides (NO₂), Sulphur oxides (SO₂), carbon monoxide (CO), particulate matter (PM), photochemical oxidants (ozone and lead Pb), along with a variety of airborne heavy metals and volatile organic compounds (VOCS) (Augustine, 2012).

Augustine (2012) affirmed that in urban areas, automobiles form a significant source of a number of air pollutants namely: particulates, nitrogen oxide, hydrocarbon, carbon monoxide and lead. These pollutants are produced when fuel is burnt under less-than-ideal conditions. Emission from automobile have been implicated in several respiratory and other diseases as well as in the degradation of the environment, including formation of acid rains implicated in biodiversity loss and defacing of physical structures (Omar, 2010). Equally air pollution can occur as a result of activities of natural conditions such as ash from volcanic explosion, storm and forest fire (Augustine, 2012). It is often a combination of both natural factors as well as human activities that lead to highly unhealthy conditions in air quality (NRDC 2023). Air pollution can have a disastrous effect on all components of the environment including ground water, soil, and air. It also poses serious threat to living organisms. According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2017), air pollution constitutes the largest amongst environmental risks which has resulted to about three (3) million annual deaths due to outdoor air pollution exposure. In 2012, 11.6 percent of global deaths equivalent to 6.5 million deaths were related to outdoor air pollution. 94% of the approximately 90% of air pollution related deaths occurring in low- and middle-income countries are as a result of non-communicable diseases including cardiovascular diseases (CVDS), chronic pulmonary diseases (CO PD) and lung cancer.

With reference to the causes of air pollution, Onokerhoraye (1995) asserted that in Nigeria rapid urban growth, increasing economic and technological development and social change have brought various forms of pollution. Going further Onokerhoraye (1995) affirmed that most outdoor pollution in urban areas of Nigeria was from a combination of fossil fuels in industrial process for heating and electricity

generation and by motor vehicles. Further study indicated that another major source of air pollution in Nigerian urban centres is associated with industrialization. Onokerhoraye (1995) affirmed that in the large industrial urban centres such as Port Harcourt, pollutants are injected into the air by industries. The Sulphur dioxide and oxides of nitrogen which are released into the cloud fall as raindrops laden with Sulphuric and nitric acids (Langsberg, 1976). Other causes of air pollution in most Nigeria urban environments include household and garden refuse, human and industrial waste, bush burning and fuel combustion for commercial primary energy production (Onokerhoraye, 1995).

A pertinent question to be address at this juncture is this: is air pollution a global phenomenon? Evidence in literature indicated that air pollution is a global issue. In the United States of America, it is reported that air pollution from the oil and gas industry harms the health of people throughout Texas, thus increasing the cancer risk for millions of people and forming ozone smog that causes asthma attacks and other health problems across the state (Mc Cabe and Graham, 2017). According to United States Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) data for 2011, over 8,500 tons of hazardous toxic air pollution benzene, formaldehyde, and acetaldehyde and other compounds were emitted by the Texas Oil and Gas Industry (Mc Cabe and Graham, 2017). Exposure to these toxic gases spewed by the Oil and Gas industry raises the cancer risk above EPA'S level of concern in 82 Texas counties.

In the United Kingdom air pollution has long been considered a significant health issue, and it causes numerous other environmental problems such as damage to buildings, forests and crops (Brimblecombe 2003, Brimblecombe, and Grossi, 2010; Emberson, Ashmore, and Murray 2003). Many areas including major cities like London, are found to be significantly and regularly above legal and recommended pollution levels (Powell, 2017). Air pollution in the UK is a major cause of diseases such as asthma, lung cancer, stroke, other cancers and heart disease. It is estimated to cause forty thousand premature deaths each year, which is about 83 % of deaths, while costing around £40 billion each year (Roberts 2016, Silver, 2017)

In Asia particularly China, there is evidence that air pollution constitutes a menace to its environment. According to the Global Burden of Diseases study, ambient PM 2.5 pollution was responsible for approximately 1.4 million premature deaths in China in 2019 (Huang,2024). However, notwithstanding the level of air pollution reported in China, the Chinese government is working hard to reduce the level of air pollution.

African continent is not spared of the menace of air pollution. Karen (2024) reported that air pollution is a growing threat in Africa, and it is the second leading cause of death after malnutrition in Sub-Saharan Africa and the main environmental risk factor for death in North Africa. According to the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), outdoor air pollution is projected to increase the yearly number of premature deaths from 930, 000 in 2030 to 1.6 million by 2063.

In Nigeria, the menace of air pollution has been reported. Onokerhoraye (1995) reported that the air mantles over major urban centers in the country such as Lagos, Ibadan, Kano, Jos, Port Harcourt, Aba,

Benin and Warri are typically significantly polluted with photo-chemical smog, carbon monoxide, sulfur dioxide, hydrogen sulfide and a number of other lesser air pollutants. For example, the air over Lagos where about 38 percent of the manufacturing industries in the country are located, has since been credited with characteristic unpleasant odour with its skyline not becoming visible until about midday due to a grayish industrial haze (Yebovi, 1983; NEST, 1991).

With respect to air pollution in Port Harcourt city and environs, Augustine (2012) reported that increasing automobiles traffic in the city and use of agricultural land for constructing buildings have degraded the environment of the city. Augustine (2012) stated that the major sources of air pollutants entering the municipal districts of Port Harcourt area are old poorly maintained diesel engines, local buses running between city and suburbs. In the same vein Yakubu (2017) opined that the first observation of a high concentration of soot in different parts of Port Harcourt was in November 2016. Air pollution particularly soot pollution has contributed significantly to the unavailability of safe drinking water in the city. A break down shows that 76 percent-80 percent of people in rural areas and 50 percent-55 percent of residents in urban areas lack access to safe drinking water. This corroborates the April 2018 ranking of Port Harcourt as one of the most polluted cities in the world, with an air index of 188ug/m³ (Efekalam,2022). Similarly, Air Visual ranked Port Harcourt as “very unhealthy” for sensitive groups, having attained an air index of 207.817 ug/m³ in December 2022 (Efekalam, 2022). Recent studies conducted by some researchers on the effects of air pollution in the Port Harcourt revealed that air pollution promotes leukemia, cancer of the liver, esophagus and skin. Their findings indicated that there is a high incidence of cancer in the study area and that its prevalence is related to the prevalence of air pollution particularly soot (Ihesinachi et. al, 2019; Ewubare and Okadigwe, 2018). Air pollution equally has impact on the physical, social and economic activities in the Port Harcourt coupled with climate change.

However, successive governments (Federal and State) have made concerted efforts in tackling the problem of air pollution in Port Harcourt. The Federal Ministry of Environment declared air pollution in Port Harcourt and its environs an “Emergency Situation’ in February, 2017 (Ovuakporie 2017; Global Patriot, 2017). It subsequently issued a notice to temporarily shut down an asphalt processing plant in Port Harcourt that is spewing out thick smoke from its operation to bring the situation under control, while an investigation into the cause of the air pollution was on-going, amongst others (Yakabu, 2017). Despite these efforts, the effects of air pollution on both human health and the living environment in Port Harcourt have remained unabated. Specifically, it is pertinent to carry out an empirical study on the effects of air pollution on the socioeconomic activities in Port Harcourt. The outcome of the study will provide workable remedial measures to the menace of air pollution on the socioeconomic activities in the city and indeed other Nigerian urban areas. Therefore, the aim of this study is to assess the effects of air pollution on the socioeconomic activities in Port Harcourt.

Statement of problem

Air is one of the major components needed by human beings to survive. The quality of air human breath has a greater contribution to the comfort of his/her existence on earth. However, the source of air and its composition are very important to our daily living. The quality of air human breathe determines the human state of health (Obi, Osang, Ewona, Udoimuk, Kamgba 2013). On other hand Pollution is the presence of harmful substances in the environment at levels greater than it should be.

Thus, air pollution is caused by any undesirable substance, which enters the atmosphere and is a major problem in this modern society. Even though air pollution is usually a greater problem in cities, pollutants contaminate air in the environment. However, these substances include various gases and tiny particles, or particulates that can harm human health and damage the environment. The major hazardous pollutants in urban cities are carbon monoxide, nitric oxide, sulphur dioxide, particulate matter and smog. They may be gases, liquids, or solids. Many pollutants are emitted into the air as a result of human activities causing harm to the environment.

The soil is damaged and does not encourage farming activities, people's business and house are flooded as a result of climate change due to release of particulate of matters into the atmosphere which then fall as precipitation. Waters are polluted by precipitation leading business owner to have alternative means of water source for their production and services; thereby increase the cost of production. This also results to goods increase (high cost of goods) to the public. Furthermore, the increased deterioration of ambient air quality in Port Harcourt, led to a state protest in February 2017. There were experiences of black soot settling in nostrils, on cars, floors, roofs, windows, bathtubs, bathroom, kitchen sinks and household furniture surfaces resulting in frequent cleaning of affected surfaces and places. According to Yakubu (2018), Potable domestic and rainwater were equally affected mostly in area such as Abuloma, Iwofe, Rupokwu, Okrika, and Woji, Rumuigbo, Eleme, and Oyigbo Local Government Councils, as well as Ogoni area.

Therefore, precautionary measures against these gases and chemicals release into the atmosphere are generally poor and most of the industries in Port Harcourt lack resources to curtail the effect of these pollution contaminant, although the Rivers State government has short down some industries in Aluu area of the state and was able to achieve little reduction on black shoot air pollution based on her action. The pubic are also ignorant of air pollution consequences thereby promoting and not curtailing the activities which brings about air pollution in the area (Obi, Osang, Ewona, Udoimuk, Kamgba 2013). In view of these problems, the researchers therefore focus on assessment of effect of Air Pollution on socio-economic activities of Port Harcourt, River's State.

Aim and Objective

The aim of this research is to assess the effects of air pollution on socio-economic activities of Port Harcourt, Rivers State.

The specific objectives of this research are as follows:

1. To find out the major sources of air pollution in the study area
2. To examine the effects of air pollution on the social activities of residents in the study area.

Research Questions

1. What are the major sources of air pollution in the study area?
2. What are the effects of air pollution on the social activities of residents in the study area.

Hypothesis

H₁: There is no significance effect of air pollution on the social activities of residents in the study area Port Harcourt.

Scope and Delimitation

The scope of this research includes the identifications the challenges and setbacks which are encountered by business, farmers and other individuals due to air pollution effects. Since air pollution does not only effect health but also damage the atmosphere which then result to climate change issues. Thus, the climate change issues lead to the damage of soil nutrient for agriculture, causes flooding, destroys the aquatic lives in the water and cause several harms to the environment. Others issues include effect on human activities i.e., location of business. The research examines the impact of air pollution on the socio-economic activities of residents in Port Harcourt and recommends any possible prospects from advancement and improvement on air pollution policy in Nigeria. However, this research is limited to the above and the researcher collected relevant information from individual business owner, farmer and other places where there are economic actives which are as a result of air pollution. The data collected were tabulated and the percentage of each tables determined. Graphical representations were used for the analysis. As a final step, this research will also provide recommendations to the impediments of our society as orchestrated by our laws and governmental organizations using responses from the data collection and analysis.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Framework

Air pollution occurs when air contains harmful substances different from its natural constituents, which are detrimental to human health and the environment (Natural Resources Defense Council, 2018). However, Air pollution in particular has been the growing cause of morbidity and mortality, dating back to the Great London Smog of 1952 (Kirby, 2013). These substances can be in the form of gases, particulate matter (PM) or even energy such as heat or noise (Godish and Davis, 2015).

Air pollution is arguably more prevalent in countries where natural resources mining, at the artisanal and regulated levels, are conducted devoid of best practice or acceptable standards (Efobi, Belmondo, Orkoh, Atata, Akinyemi & Beecroft 2019). In such countries, like Nigeria, human health, the environment and other activities are exposed to disproportionate and avoidable levels of air pollution which poses significant risks the population of the area.

Air Pollution and Climate Changes

Air pollution and climate change are closely related. However, climate is the other side of the same coin that reduces the quality of the earth (D'Amato, Pawankar, and Vitale & Maurizia 2016). The onset of global industrialisation in the 18 and 19th centuries brought about peculiar socio-economic issues, many of which resulted in attendant environmental and health challenges (Kirby, 2013; Godish and Davis, 2015). Pollutants such as black carbon, methane, tropospheric ozone, and aerosols affect the amount of incoming sunlight. As a result, the temperature of the Earth increases, resulting in the melting of ice, icebergs, and glaciers.

Air pollution is arguably more prevalent in countries where natural resources mining, at the artisanal and regulated levels, are conducted devoid of best practice or acceptable standards (Efobi et al., 2019). Recently, in Europe, eradicated diseases seem to be emerging due to the migration of population, for example, cholera, poliomyelitis, tick-borne encephalitis, and malaria (Castelli & Sulis 2017). The spread of epidemics is associated with natural climate disasters and storms, which seem to occur more frequently nowadays (Manisalidis et al. 2020). Malnutrition and disequilibrating of the immune system are also associated with the emerging infections affecting public health and environment (Manisalidis et al. 2020). The Chikungunya virus “took the airplane” from the Indian Ocean to Europe, as outbreaks of the disease were registered in Italy (Lindh, Argentini, Remoli, Fortuna, Faggioni, & Benedetti 2019) as well as autochthonous cases in France (Calba, Guerbois-Galla, Franke, Jeannin, Auzet-Caillaud, Grard, Pigaglio, Decoppet 2017).

An increase in cryptosporidiosis in the United Kingdom and in the Czech Republic seems to have occurred following flooding (Menne & Murray (2013). As stated previously, aerosols compounds are tiny in size and considerably affect the climate. They are able to dissipate sunlight (the albedo phenomenon) by dispersing a quarter of the sun's rays back to space and have cooled the global temperature over the last 30 years (Manisalidis et al. 2020). In countries, like Nigeria, human health is exposed to disproportionate and avoidable levels of air pollution which poses significant health risks to local populations. Nigeria is battling with rising air pollution concerns. The vast oil exploration and production activities and high population growth rate are major contributors to this problem (Olowoporoku, Longhurst & Barnes 2012; Yakubu, 2018). As a result of more than 50 years of oil and gas exploration and production, Nigeria suffers extensive environmental degradation occasioned by gas flaring (Brandt, 2020) and oil spills (UNEP, 2011a; Zabbey, Sam & Onyebuchi, 2017). Despite Nigeria's commitment to climate action, the country is primarily dependent on fossil fuels, a major source of flared gas (Brandt, 2020). In the Niger Delta region, the hub of Nigeria's oil and gas production, air pollution has been attributed to use of biomass fuel like firewood, indiscriminate burning of vegetation and refuse, traffic and industrial emissions, and gas flaring (Godson, 2011). Artisanal refining (small scale and unregulated burning of hydrocarbons to derive petrol, diesel and kerosene) of crude oil in

Rivers State has also been shown to have detrimental effects on the atmosphere through the release of carbon dioxide, methane and other gases (UNEP, 2011b; Ogele and Egobueze, 2020).

Rivers State, one of the nine states in the crude oil rich Niger Delta region of Nigeria is the hub of oil and gas exploration in the region, and thus faces increasing air pollution problems. Studies have documented various effects of air pollution in Rivers State, notably acid rain and more recently, soot pollution (Nduka and Orisakwe, 2010; Yakubu, 2018). The presence of soot largely affects cultural activities and lifestyle of residents as people spend more time indoors making community members communicate and interact less with themselves. According to Allen, (2017) in his study on impact of black soot in Port Harcourt; noted that residents in Port Harcourt tend to spend most of their time indoors rather than outdoors, with parents restricting their children from outdoor activities out of fear of the impact of soot on children's health. A proportion of respondents also indicated plans to relocate to other cities, thereby occasioning an economic imbalance on the communities if there is depletion in human resources in polluted cities (Allen, 2017).

Furthermore, the fine particles in soot (PM_{2.5}) pose peculiar health challenges. When inhaled, the size of these fine particles enables them to penetrate deep into bronchiolar tissue causing oxidative stress and pulmonary inflammation, and possible deoxyribonucleic acid damage (Niranjan and Thakur, 2017; Valavanidis et al., 2013). Climate and weather also affect the duration, timing, and intensity of outbreaks strongly and change the map of infectious diseases in the globe (Bezirtzoglou, Dekas & Charvalos 2011). Mosquito-transmitted parasitic or viral diseases are extremely climate-sensitive, as warming firstly shortens the pathogen incubation period and secondly shifts the geographic map of the vector. Similarly, water-warming following climate changes leads to a high incidence of waterborne infections. These effects of air pollution also affect the residents in Port Harcourt, and other African countries cities who are major contributors to air pollution.

Environmental Impact of Air Pollution

Air pollution is harming not only human health but also the environment (Ashfaq&Sharma 2012) in which we live. The most important environmental effects are as follows: Acid rain in wet rain fog, snow or dry particulates and gas precipitation containing toxic amounts of nitric and sulfuric acids. They are able to acidify the water and soil environments, damage trees and plantations, and even damage buildings and outdoor sculptures, constructions, and statues. Haze is produced when fine particles are dispersed in the air and reduce the transparency of the atmosphere. It is caused by gas emissions in the air coming from industrial facilities, power plants, automobiles, and trucks. Ozone occurs both at ground level and in the upper level (stratosphere) of the Earth's atmosphere. Stratospheric ozone is protecting us from the Sun's harmful ultraviolet (UV) rays. In contrast, ground-level ozone is harmful to human health and is a pollutant. Unfortunately, stratospheric ozone is gradually damaged by ozone-depleting substances (i.e., chemicals, pesticides, and aerosols). If this protecting stratospheric ozone

layer is thinned, then UV radiation can reach our Earth, with harmful effects for human life skin cancer and crops damages (Manisalidis et al. 2020).

In plants, ozone penetrates through the stomata, inducing them to close, which blocks CO₂ transfer and induces a reduction in photosynthesis (Manisalidis et al 2020). Global climate change is an important issue that concerns mankind. As is known, the “greenhouse effect” keeps the Earth’s temperature stable. Unhappily, anthropogenic activities have destroyed this protecting temperature effect by producing large amounts of greenhouse gases, and global warming is mounting, with harmful effects on human health, animals, forests, wildlife, agriculture, and the water environment. A report states that global warming is adding to the health risks of poor people (Manderson 2019). People living in poorly constructed buildings in warm-climate countries are at high risk for heat-related health problems as temperatures mount (Manderson 2019). Wildlife is burdened by toxic pollutants coming from the air, soil, or the water ecosystem and, in this way; animals can develop health problems when exposed to high levels of pollutants. Reproductive failure and birth effects have been reported. Eutrophication is occurring when elevated concentrations of nutrients (especially nitrogen) stimulate the blooming of aquatic algae, which can cause a dis-equilibrating in the diversity of fish and their deaths. Without a doubt, there is a critical concentration of pollution that an ecosystem can tolerate without being destroyed, which is associated with the ecosystem’s capacity to neutralize acidity. The Canada Acid Rain Program established this load at 20 kg/ha/yr (Manisalidis et al 2020). Hence, air pollution has deleterious effects on both soil and water (Zuhara&Isaifan2018). Concerning PM as an air pollutant, its impact on crop yield and food productivity has been reported. Its impact on watery bodies is associated with the survival of living organisms and fishes and their productivity potential (Zuhara et al. 2018). Impairment in photosynthetic rhythm and metabolism is observed in plants exposed to the effects of ozone (Zuhara et al. 2018). Sulfur and nitrogen oxides are involved in the formation of acid rain and are harmful to plants and marine organisms. Lastly, the toxicity associated with lead and other metals is the main threat to our ecosystems (air, water, and soil) and living creatures (Zuhara et al 2018).

Health Effect of Air Pollution

The most common air pollutants are ground-level ozone and Particulates Matter (PM) (Manisalidis et al. 2020). Air pollution is distinguished into two main types: Outdoor pollution is the ambient air pollution. Indoor pollution is the pollution generated by household combustion of fuels. People exposed to high concentrations of air pollutants experience disease symptoms and states of greater and lesser seriousness. These effects are grouped into short- and long-term effects affecting health and social economic activities as well as the environment. Susceptible populations that need to be aware of health protection measures include old people, children, and people with diabetes and predisposing heart or lung disease, especially asthma. As extensively stated previously, according to a recent epidemiological study from Harvard School of Public Health, the relative magnitudes of the short- and long-term effects

have not been completely clarified (Kloog, Ridgway, Koutrakis, and Coull & Schwartz 2013) due to the different epidemiological methodologies and to the exposure errors. New models are proposed for assessing short- and long-term human exposure data more successfully (Kloog et al. 2013). Thus, short- and long-term health effects have general concerns which are dependent on environmental conditions, dose, and individual susceptibility. Short-term effects are temporary and range from simple discomfort, such as irritation of the eyes, nose, skin, throat, wheezing, coughing and chest tightness, and breathing difficulties, to more serious states, such as asthma, pneumonia, bronchitis, and lung and heart problems. Short-term exposure to air pollution can also cause headaches, nausea, and dizziness. These problems can be aggravated by extended long-term exposure to the pollutants, which is harmful to the neurological, reproductive, and respiratory systems and causes cancer and even, rarely, deaths.

Theoretical Review

Stakeholder's Theory

The theoretical framework upon which this study is premised is stakeholder's theory.

The stakeholder's theory is more suitable to this study because environmental challenges involve not just a single actor but multiple actors. Freeman evidently is one of the pioneers behind the theory of stakeholders; and the term "stakeholder theory" is now commonly used among researchers (Friedman & Miles, 2006; Andreas & Johan 2011). He propounded this theory consequent upon his belief that stakeholders "should be used to modify the overall view of the organization" (Friedman & Miles, 2006). Stakeholder theory focuses on simultaneously taking into consideration the interests of multiple actors (Gooyert et al., 2017). Stakeholder theory has been variously described as a viewpoint, a collection of ideas, expression, and metaphors relating to the overriding goal of maximizing stakeholder value (Haataja, 2020). Researchers and scholars of stakeholder theory emphasize the "joining together" of interests as the foundation for all business value creation (Haataja, 2020).

Due to the financial implication and unpredictable nature of increasingly regular natural disasters, environmental problem has grown to be a serious challenge for business (Haigh & Griffiths, 2007; Mills et al., 2002; Stern, 2006). Consequent upon the above Omisakin (2022) reported that we now experience severe weather that is unpredictable but increasingly common due to anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions. This is in addition to incremental climate change brought about by Earth's geographic dynamics, such as gradual changes in humidity and rainfall which has itself displaced entire civilizations (Haigh & Griffiths, 2007; Fagan, 1999, 2004). As a result, there is a need to consider the environment as an important stakeholder.

According to Freeman (2009,) as cited by (Haataja, 2020) considering stakeholder interests in management decision-making allows for "better consequences for all stakeholders because it understands that stakeholder interests are joint." Going further Freeman (2009) argues that If one stakeholder pursues its interests at the expense of others, the others will either withdraw their support or seek to establish a new network of stakeholder value creation." The stakeholder's participation in

environmental decision making by government and industry is inevitable and will grow. Building on this, Freeman (1984) outlines the need to change the way we think about business, away from old models of thinking and toward a consideration of the organization's external environment. Thus, he proposes stakeholder theory, which aims to "force organizational managers to be more responsive to the external environment" (Freeman 1984). The stakeholder idea, according to Freeman (1984), "provides a new way of thinking about strategic management, that is, how a firm can and should determine and implement strategy". In this regard, Freeman (1984) makes it abundantly clear that stakeholder theory is a new approach to the strategic management of an organization that will help to shed the old, or as he puts it, it is an approach that can "help managers view the world as it is today not as it was 30 years ago (Nick, 2011).

The forces driving the evolution of environmental stakeholder processes include: "a lack of public confidence and trust in many government agencies and corporations; greater transparency of institutions whose decisions affect environmental quality; increased societal expectations for improved environmental quality; enhanced citizens participation in stakeholder processes; the growing diffusion of information technology and an associated decentralization of decision making in large institutions; and policy commitments made by government agencies and industries to expand stakeholder participation in their decision making processes" (Terry & Timothy, 1998). The natural environment, which was once thought to be only the external environment, has become a major influencing factor in managerial decision making and is now regarded as central to marketing and management strategy (Saleem et al., 2020).

Empirical Review

Air Pollution and Air Quality Challenges Nigeria

The petroleum industry constitutes a major source of air pollution in the Niger Delta. Within this industry, production operations, such as oil and condensate spills, gas flaring and venting, as well as transportation, constitute main sources of pollutants (Fagbeja, Hill, Chatterton, Longhurst, and Akinyede 2013). Other sources include power plants, heavy industry equipment, including boilers, burners, coolants, and separators. Industries such as foundries, chemical and solvent, automobile, construction, and agriculture also contribute to air quality impairment in the Niger Delta (Ede & Edokpa 2015). Gas flaring constitutes a major environmental public health issue in Port Harcourt and other Niger Delta states. The human health consequences are diverse and include various morbidities and mortalities (Gobo, Richard & Ubong 2010). Health conditions associated with pollutants discharged in flares include asthma, cancer of the lungs, difficulties in breathing, miscarriages among pregnant women within the age 38–40, and premature deaths (ASTDR 2017). Yakubu (2017), as well as Ede & Edokpa (2015); document some other pollutants detected in the Niger Delta region and their various health effects in their assessment on pollutants originating from automobile in heavy traffic urban areas in Port-Harcourt.

However, Okonkwo, Okpala & Opara (2014) demonstrated not only the prevalence of gaseous pollutants, but also their occurrence at levels exceeding the Federal Ministry of Environment's I-hour guidelines. Average concentrations obtained for carbon monoxide (CO), sulphur dioxide (SO₂), nitrogen oxide (NO₂), and hydrocarbons (HC) were above the Federal Environmental Protection Agency (FEPA) (now FME) standards. Additionally, their study included a comparative analysis of the quantities obtained at peak periods both in the mornings and in the evenings of each sampling day. Their findings suggest that the ambient concentration of pollutants at the two sampling sites were in most cases higher in the mornings between the hours of 8 a.m. and 9 a.m. than in the evenings between 4:30 p.m. and 5:30 p.m. (Okonkwo et al. 2014). Although, the differences for the sampling times were not so significant, readings obtained for Monday through Saturday were much higher than those that were obtained for Sunday, during which time fewer industrial activities and traffic occur (Okonkwo et al. 2014). Ede et al. (2015), analysed air samples obtained from 16 communities in the Niger Delta including Port-Harcourt for their CO, SO₂, NO₂, HC, and suspended particulate matter (SPM) composition. In most cases, the quantities of pollutants exceeded the WHO Air Quality Guidelines (Ede et al. 2015). In particular, the particulate load was above the WHO specification for both particle 2.5 microns and below (PM_{2.5}) and particles 10 microns and below (PM₁₀) annual mean and 24-h mean (PM_{2.5}: 10 µg/m³ annual mean, 25 µg/m³ 24-h mean; PM₁₀: 20 µg/m³ annual mean, 50 µg/m³ 24-h mean) (Ede et al. 2015). Although the value range obtained for each pollutant was dependent on the time of the day and year or season nearness to point source and extent of anthropological engagement. Amongst the 16 locations, Port-Harcourt had the highest mean SPM load. Association of high SPM loads with such factors as high numbers of oil fields and gas flare sources; ongoing construction activities, location on or proximity to highly engaged roads, and industrial facilities occurred (Ede et al. 2015).

Thus Weli (2014) conducted extensive research involving in-depth quantitative analysis of the spatial and seasonal atmospheric levels of particles 10 microns and below (PM₁₀) in Port Harcourt, and the environmental implication of their occurrence at measured concentrations. Relative quantities of the pollutant in various areas based on land use, and the time of the year were compared with land use, including commercial, high-density residential, low-density residential, industrial, and rural. PM₁₀ sampling and analysis was conducted in the dry, transition, and wet seasons. Findings suggest that land use and season influenced atmospheric concentrations of PM₁₀ (Weli, 2014). In terms of land use, the commercial and industrial areas had the highest values in the dry season. The Low-density residential areas had the lowest PM₁₀ value. The seasonal total atmospheric loading for the wet, transition, and dry seasons were 3436.1 µg/m³, 8573.12 µg/m³ and 16,148.87 µg/m³ (Weli, 2014). The study also suggests a statistically significant difference in the seasonal PM₁₀ concentration amongst the land use types. People who live and work around the areas with a high concentration of particulate matter (PM) are susceptible to respiratory disease infection and includes high-density residential areas (Weli 2014).

Furthermore, the Ministry of Environment in Port Harcourt took action by analysing air samples from various sites in the city and found out to be 11 times higher than WHO specifications for PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀. This non-compliance was tackled by shutting down the Chinese Government Company (CGC), H&H Engineering Company, and AUC Asphalt Company located in Aluu community, found to be the location of high-volume discharge of emissions thereby contravening environmental regulations. Illegal refineries, burning of tires, gas flaring, liquefied natural gas (LNG) operations and processes, petro-chemical companies, and refineries were other suspected sources of air pollution that resulted to decrease in economic activities and causing most business to start move to a safer location and other cities. (Yakubu 2018; the Guardian Nigeria News 2017).

Air Quality History in Port Harcourt

Residents of the city of Port Harcourt started experiencing particle (soot) pollution since the last quarter of 2016 (Yakubu 2018). The residents state their clothes and everything outside is covered with a layer of black soot (Chris 2018). Official PM_{2.5} information from the state's environmental commissioner, Roseline Konya, states a high reading of 270 micrograms per cubic meter for air pollution in the city from a 2016 sampling (Undark Magazine 2018). According to the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency's (EPA) index Air Quality Index (AQI), a reading of 0 - 50 is good, readings between 200 - 300 which Port Harcourt falls under is considered unhealthy for everyone and E.P.A advises residents of such areas to avoid heavy and prolonged exertion, and move activities indoors (US EPA 2014). "For a 15-month period ending in June 2018, air quality of Port Harcourt was in the unhealthy range on 240 days, with 85 days ranking very unhealthy, and 13 days as hazardous (Cunningham 2018). The increased deterioration of ambient air quality led to a state protest in February 2017. There were experiences of black soot settling in nostrils, on cars, floors, roofs, windows, bathtubs, bathroom, kitchen sinks and household furniture surfaces resulting in frequent cleaning of affected surfaces and places. Potable, domestic and rainwater were equally affected. Abuloma, Iwofe, Rupokwu, Okrika, and Woji were mostly affected with other areas such as Rumuigbo, Eleme, and Oyigbo Local Government Councils, as well as Ogoni (Yakubu 2018; The Guardian Nigeria News 2017). The covering of the haze of soot in most parts of the city have resulted in visibility impairment by PM_{2.5}, soil, and water deposition and disruption in ecosystem diversity. This also made the city dwellers to spend more time indoors than outdoors. Residents in cities such as Rumosi and Rumuodumanya in Obio/Akpor Council have relocated to other safe cities leading to decline in business activities. (Yakubu 2018; The Guardian Nigeria News 2017).

Black Soot as a Result of Air Pollution in Port Harcourt

Black soot is a type of air pollutant; it is about 2.5mm diameter. As a pollutant, it comprises a variety of other pollutants like chemical acids, metals, and dust particles. By its nature, it can take the form of a solid, liquid, or gaseous state. Ordinarily, soot is a type of product of burning fossil fuels like oil refining

and smokes from vehicles. Given its small particle nature, soot particles are emitted into the air while some others form gas particles that can travel thousands of miles from their source.

Over the years, soot has been classified as a threat to economic activities and public health as public health generally, is concerned with promoting and protecting the health of people and the community where they live, learn, work and play (American Public Health Association, 2020). By this, an incidence that is capable of affecting negatively the safety and well-being or improvement in the health of the people is considered a public health problem.

Niranjan and Thakur (2017), in a study titled “The toxicological mechanisms of environmental soot which is known as black carbon and carbon black focus on oxidation stressed and inflammatory pathways” established that soot and carbon black can constitute public health problem. In their study, it was revealed that soot and carbon black can cause many diseases. That soot, apart from that it is carcinogenic, can also lead to multiple diseases to man. Thus, Niranjan and Thakur (2017) in their studies also revealed that soot particles from the 1991 oil fields of Kuwait induced genetic mutation which is capable of damaging DNA.

A recent study by Kalagbor, Orji and Ekpete (2019) titled “exposure to heavy metals in soot samples and cancer risk assessment in Port Harcourt, Nigeria” reaffirms other studies in this. These scholars confirmed that soot causes leukemia, cancer of the liver oesophagus, and skin. The research equally asserts that there is a high incidence of cancer in the area of this study and that its prevalence is related to the presents of soot in the area of their study. A separate study by Akutu (2018) titled “Health issues to know about soot, preventive measures” revealed that long-time exposure to soot can cause pneumonias.

However, Whyte, Tamuno-Wari, and Kabari (2020) in a survey of the resident perception of the effects of pollution in Rivers State Nigeria, equally confirmed that residents are not just aware of the soot problem, but they claim that soot is the main cause of chronic cough; eye, nose, throat and skin irritation.

Feng, Gao, Liao, Zhou, and Wang (2016) in a related study highlighted that the absorption of the pollutant into target cells in the human body could harm cellular physiological/biochemical developments. This according to these scholars can result in adverse birth outcomes plus the growth of diabetes mellitus, cardiopulmonary diseases among others.

Weli and Adekunle (2014) in a study of environmental risk factors and hospital-based cancers in two Nigerian cities established a close relationship between air pollution including soot with morbidities like respiratory diseases, traumatic skin, outgrowth and respiratory health condition, child deformities, stillbirth, miscarriage.

Observing further Yakubu (2017), claim that findings from different studies relate adverse health problems like eye and skin disorders with people who are frequently exposed to polluted air. Yakubu even Humanist Eco-Marxists like Clark have also established a similar relationship between man and

nature. This theory specifically claims that man and nature are in an interdependence relationship. This sentiment of the close affinity between nature and man is further emphasized by Rift theory which sees the relationship as dynamic and that the dynamics are between humans and non-humans in the natural world which for them are distinct entities, but are united within one metabolic system.

Study Area

Figure 3.1: Map of Port Harcourt and Environs

SOURCE:https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Figure-1-Map-of-Port-Harcourt-City-Local-Government-Area-and-its-environs-showing-sample_fig1_334964294 and edited by (researcher 2022).

METHODOLOGY

This section discusses research design, methodology and sources of data required to prosecute the current study. It highlights the techniques used in the data analysis for the purpose of making generalization.

Research Design

For the purpose of this study, survey research design was adopted. Survey research provides a quantitative or numeric description of trends, attitudes, or opinions of a population by studying a sample of that population. It includes cross-sectional and longitudinal studies using questionnaire, or structured interviews for data collection with the intent of generalizing from a sample to a population (Babble 1990, Okereke, 2017).

4.2 Data Needs

The following data are required for the research:

Research Objective 1: To find out the major sources of air pollution in the study area.

Data required:

- (a) Sources of air pollution in the study area.
- (b) Air index of Port Harcourt
- (c) Components of air pollution.

Research Objective 2: To examine the effects of air pollution on the social activities of Port Harcourt residents.

Data Required:

- a) Effects on social activities
- b) Effects on economic activities
- c) Effects on the physical activities
- d) Effects on health of the residents and other organisms

Population of the Study

The population of Port Harcourt Local Government Area after the 1991 census was 440, 399 (National Population Commission, 1992). The above figure is projected to the year 2024 to give the figure currency and we have 1,245,316. The population of Port Harcourt Local Government Area from the 1991 Census is presented in Table 4:1.

Table 4.1: Population of Port Harcourt Local Government Area, 1991 Census.

S/N	Locality	1991 both sexes	2024 both sexes
1.	Nkpolu-Oroworukwu	52,613	148,774.
2.	Mgbundukwu	55,682	157,402.
3.	Otumuonyo	44,183	124,936.
4.	Oromerezimbu	6,595	18,649.
5.	Orominieke	21,377	60,448.
6.	Rumuoparaeli	14,133	39,964.
7.	Nkpolu-Orogbum	3,423	9,679.
8.	Ochiri	6,072	17,170.
9.	Elekahia	15,302	43,269.
10.	Ogbunabali	15,014	42,455.
11.	Orije Old GRA	6,482	18,329.
12.	Town	12,369	34,976.
13.	Bundu	16,266	45,995.
14.	Nembe Water Side	71,388	201,864.
15.	Nkpogu	20,402	57,691.
16.	Amadi Ama	7,034	19,890.
17.	Ukukalama	691	1,954.
18.	Somiari Ama	1,296	3,665.
19.	Fimie Ama	1,250	3,535.
20.	Ozuboko	4,484	12,679.
21.	Borikiri	39,214	110,885.
22.	Ishmael Orupabo	945	2,672.
23.	Abuloma	10,454	29,561.
24.	Okuku-Ama	5,603	15,844.
25.	Azubie-Ama	8,127	22,980.
26.	LGA Total	440,399	1,245,316.

Source: National Population Commission 1991 census, Abuja.

From the above presentation the population of the current study is 1,245,316 estimated residents of Port Harcourt Local Government Area in the year 2024.

Determination of Sample Size and Sampling Technique

With respect to determination of sample size, this study adopted the Yaro Yamani (1964) method.

According to Yaro Yamani; to determine a sample from a population,

$$n = \frac{N}{\dots}$$

$$1+(Ne\ 2)$$

Where;

n = Sample size

N = population size

N = Error limit

Given the above scenario we can proceed to determine the sample size of the residents of Port Harcourt Local Government Area. Substituting in the Yaro-Yamani formula stated above:

$$n = 1,245,316$$

$$1+(1,245,316(0.05)^2)$$

$$n = 1,245,316$$

$$1+(1,245,316 (0.0025))$$

$$n = 1,245,316$$

$$1+3,113.29$$

$$n = 1,245,316$$

$$3,114.29 = 399.87$$

$$n = 400 \text{ approx.}$$

From the above, the sample size of this study is 400.

4.5.1 Sampling Technique

Two types of sampling technique used in this study were stratified sampling and purposive sampling techniques. Stratified sampling technique was applied to divide Port Harcourt Local Government Area into twenty-five (25) homogenous localities as shown in table 4.1. Then in each stratum or locality, purposive sampling was used to select specific residential building and heads of household according to the sample size of each locality.

Following from the above, to determine the sample size of each locality from the Port Harcourt Local Government Area sample size of 400, Bourley's sample size proportion allocation formula as stated in the equation below was used. According to Bourley's sample size allocation formular:

$$nb = n(h)$$

$$N$$

Where;

nb = Sample proportion allocated to a given locality

n = Population allocated to respondent groups

N = Population of the study

h = Total sample size.

1. To work out the sample size of Nkpolu –Oroworukwu

$$nb = 148,774 \times 400$$

$$1,245,316 \times 1 = 47.7$$

= 48 approx.

Sample size for the rest of the localities were similarly worked out see appendix ii. The estimated population of each locality and their sample sizes are shown in table 4.2.

Table 4.2: Population of Localities and Their Sample Sizes.

S/N	Localities in Port Harcourt	Population	Sample sizes
1.	Nkpolu-Oroworukwu	148,774	48
2.	Mgbudukwu	157,452	51
3.	Otumuonyo	124,936	40
4.	Oromerezimbu	18,649	6
5.	Orominieke	60,448	19
6.	Nkpolu-Orogbum	9,679	3
7.	Rumuopareli	39,964	13
8.	Ochiri	17,170	6
9.	Elekahia	43,269	14
10.	Ogbunabali	42,455	14
11.	Oriji-Old GRA	18,329	6
12.	Town	34,976	11
13.	Bundu	45,995	14
14.	Nembe water side	201,864	65
15.	Nkpogu	57,691	19
16.	Amadi Ama	19,890	6
17.	Ukukalama	1,954	1
18.	Somieri Ama	3,665	1
19.	Fimie Ama	3,535	1
20.	Ozuboko	12,679	4
21.	Borikiri	110,885	36
22.	Ishmael Orupabo	2,672	1
23.	Abuloma	29,561	9
24.	Okuku-Ama	15,844	5
25.	Azubie –Ama	22,980	7
	LGA-Total	1,245,316	400

Source: Researcher's Field work.

Sample size of localities

- i) Nkpolu-Oroworukwu
nb = 148,774 x 400

$$1,245,316 \div 47.7 = 48$$

ii) Mgbundukwu

$$nb = 157,402 \times 400$$

$$1,245,316 \div 50.5 = 51$$

The sample size of other localities is presented in Appendix 1.

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected from the field was tabulated and compiled in frequency based on the numbers of respondent in each questionnaire and the percentage of each table determined. Descriptive statistical such as frequency distribution table, bar chart, pie chart and percentages were used to describe and analyze the data collected from the field while inferential statistics were used to test the hypothesis on the effect of of air pollutions on the social and economic activities in Port Harcourt Local Government Area, Rivers State.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Research Objective One: To Find Out the Major Sources of Air Pollution in the Study Area.

This section presents and analyses questions relating to research objective one.

Showing Respondents Who Were Aware of Air Pollution Issues in Port Harcourt Local Government Area.

Respondents who were aware of air pollution issues in Port Harcourt Local Government Area. are presented and analyzed in Table 5.3.

Table 5.3: Showing Respondents Who Were Aware of Air Pollution Issues in Port Harcourt Local Government Area.

S/N	Are you Aware of Air Pollution Issues in Port Harcourt?	Frequency (F)	Percentage %
a.	Yes	384	96
b.	No	16	4
	Total	400	100

Source: Researchers Field work, 2024.

Table 5.3 above shows that 96% of the individual's resident in Port Harcourt were aware of air pollution issues in the area while only 4% were not aware of air pollution issues in the study area. This means that the inhabitants of Port Harcourt Local Government Area were conscious of air pollution and its effects within the study area.

Major Sources of Air Pollution in Port Harcourt Local Government Area.

The major sources of air pollution in Port Harcourt Local Government Area are presented and analyzed in Table 5.4.

Table 5.4: Showing the Major Sources of Air Pollution in Port Harcourt LGA

S/N	Respondent	Frequency (f)	Percentage %
a.	Industrial Activities	180	45
b.	Farming Activities	12	3
c.	Illegal Banking	176	44
d.	Traffic Congestion	4	1
e.	All of the above	28	7
	Total	400	100

Source: Researchers Field Work, 2024.

Table 5.4 shows the major sources of air pollutions in Port Harcourt Local Government Area. It was discovered from the survey that industrial activities and illegal bunkering activities were the major sources of air pollution in the city of Port Harcourt with 45% and 44% responses respectively while the farming activities and traffic congestion only account for 3% and 1% of total responses respectively. This means that industrial activities by company and illegal bunkering in the area by some individuals constituted the major sources of air pollution in the study area. However, this is in line with the study conducted by scholars in Niger Delta region, the hub of Nigeria’s oil and gas production, that air pollution has been attributed to the use of biomass fuel like firewood, indiscriminate burning of vegetation and refuse, traffic and industrial emissions, and gas flaring (Whyte et al. 2020).

Research Objective Two: To Examine the Effects of Air Pollution on the Social Activities of the Inhabitants of Port Harcourt Local Government Area.

This section presents and analyses questions relating to research objective two.

5.3.1: The Level of Effect of Air Pollution on Social Activities in Port Harcourt Local Government Area.

The level of effect of air pollution on social activities in Port Harcourt Local Government Area is presented and analyzed in Table 5.5.

Table 5.5: Showing the Level of Effect of Air Pollution on Social Activities in Port Harcourt Local Government Area.

S/N	Responses	Frequency (f)	Percentage %
a.	No Effect	39	10
b.	Minor Effect	47	12
c.	Neutral	20	5
d.	Moderate	51	13
e.	Major Effect	243	60
	Total	400	100

Source: Researchers Field Work, 2024.

Table 5.5, shows the level of effect of air pollution on daily social activities in Port Harcourt Local Government Area. From the above figure, 10 % of the respondents reported no effect, 12% reported minor effect, 5% reported neutral while 13% and 61% reported moderate effect and major effect respectively. Thus, it can be summarized from Table 5.5 that air pollution had a major effect on activities of residents of Port Harcourt Local Government Area, Rivers State as respondents reported 61% as major effect of pollution on their daily activities. Plate 5.1 equally illustrates air pollution effects on the environment of Abuloma.

Plate 5.1: Showing Air Pollution Effect on the Environment of Abuloma.

Source: Researchers data collection

Categories of Air Pollution Effect on Social Activities in Port Harcourt Local Government Area.

Table 5.6: Showing Categories of Air Pollution Effect on Social Activities in Port Harcourt Local Government Area.

In What Ways Can You Categorize the Effects of Air pollution on Social Activities			
S/N	Responses	Frequency (f)	Percentage %
a.	Leads to Health Issues	35	9
b.	Results to the shutdown of social and recreational activities	164	41
c.	Damage of pool water and roof top due to black soot	126	31
d.	All of the above	67	17
e.	Others	8	2
	Total	400	100

Source: Researchers Field work 2024.

Table 5.6 shows the categories of air pollution effects on social activities in the study area. It was observed from the survey and analysis that air pollution has resulted to the shutdown of several social activities in the state. This accounted for 41% of total responses. The responses from the survey shows that 31% of the respondent in the study area agreed to the fact that air pollutions had damaged pool waters and roof tops due to black soot in the area, 41% of the responses from the field agreed that air pollution resulted to the shutdown of some social activities in the place due health and safety of the customers. However, the effect of health issues and other issues as specified by the respondents in the area are 9% and 2% representatively while 17% of the respondents agreed that all the categories of effect lead to an effect on social activities of those residents in highly polluted area in Port Harcourt, Rivers State.

The Extent of Air Pollution on Social Activities in Port Harcourt Local Government Area.

Table 5.7 presents and analyses the extent of air pollution on social activities in Port Harcourt Local Government Area.

Table 5.7: Showing the Extent of Air Pollution Effect on Social Activities in Port Harcourt Local Government Area

To What Extent Has the Effects of Air Pollution Affected Social Activities?			
S/N	Responses	Frequency (f)	Percentage %
a.	Very great extent	173	43
b.	Great extent	110	28
c.	Moderate	59	15
d.	Low extent	31	8
e.	Very low extent	27	6
	Total	400	100

Source: Researchers Field workers 2024.

Table 5.7 shows the extent of air pollution effects on social activities in Port Harcourt Local Government Area, Rivers State. It was observed from the table that 43% of the respondents reported very great extent, 28% reported great extent, 15% reported moderate extent while 8% and 6% reported low extent and very low extent respectively. The above analysis strongly suggests that air pollution to a great extent has an effect on social activities of residents of Port Harcourt Local Government Area as 43% and 27% of the respondents reported very great extent and great extent respectively.

Hypothesis Testing

Testing Hypothesis (1)

HO₁: There is no significant effect of air pollution on the social activities of residents in the study area PortHarcourt Local Government Area.

Table 5.16: There is no significance effect of air pollution on the social activities of residents in the study area

SUMMARY OUTPUT

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.121774788
R Square	0.014829099
Adjusted R Square	0.004977739
Standard Error	1.273712946
Observations	102

ANOVA					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	2.4420037	2.4420037	1.50523113	0.222748951
Residual	100	162.2344669	1.622344669		
Total	101	164.6764706			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>	<i>Lower 95.0%</i>	<i>Upper 95.0%</i>
Intercept	4.700715929	0.422585151	11.12371297	3.46104E-19	3.862319025	5.53911283	3.862319025	5.53911283
To what extent has the effect of this Air pollution affected your social participation?	-0.126182562	0.102848449	-1.226878613	0.222748951	-0.330230955	0.07786583	-0.33023095	0.07786583

Researchers Data analysis output 2022.

From the table above, the significance F (0.222748951) has a relationship with the P-value of extent of Air pollution effect on social activities (0.222748951), hence to an extent air pollution has an effect on social activities of residence in Port Harcourt. Furthermore, since the significance F (0.222748951) is greater than significance level (0.05), the null hypothesis (**H₀₁**); There is no significance effect of air pollution on the social activities of residents in the study area PortHarcourt LGA is rejected and the alternate hypothesis (**H_{a1}**); There is a significance effect of air pollution on social activities of residents in Port Harcourt LGA, Rivers State is accepted. However, it can be concluded that air pollution to a great extent has an effect on social activities of residents in Port Harcourt LGA, Rivers state.

Discussion of Findings

Research Objective One: To find out the major sources of Air Pollution in the study Area.

With respect to research objective one, our findings indicated that the major sources of air pollution in Port Harcourt Local Government Are where industrial and illegal banking activities.

The above anthropogenic activities accounted for 45% and 44% of total responses respectively (See table 5.4). The above findings collaborate the findings of Godson (2011) UNEP (2011 b), Ogele and Egobueze (2020) that in the Niger Delta region, air pollution has been attributed to the use of biomass fuel like traffic and industrial emission as well as artisanal refining of crude oil. The above findings further agreed with the findings of Augustine (2012) that the major sources of air pollution entering the municipal district of Port Harcourt area were industrial sources of air pollution resulting from the activities of cement industries, petrochemical industries and petroleum refineries. These constitute major sources of greenhouse gass emission. The Implication of the above findings for planning is that stake holders should come up with well-articulated policies that will minimize the incidence of air pollution arising from industrial sources and illegal banking.

Research Objective Two: To explore the effects of air pollution on the social activities of the inhabitants of Port Harcourt Local Government Area.

With reference to research objective two, research findings indicated that the major effects of air pollution on social activities of the inhabitants of the study area relates to the shutdown of social and recreational activities. This is followed by damage of pool water and roof top due to black soot. Thirdly, air pollution is known to have contributed immensely to health-related problems. The health effects of air pollution agree with the findings of Niranjan and Thakur (2017), in their study titled; “the toxicological mechanisms of environmental soot and black carbon can constitute public health problem”. They affirmed that soot apart from being carcinogenic, could also lead to multiple diseases to man. Niranjan and Thakur (2017) in their studies also revealed that soot particles from the 1991 oil fields of Kuwait induced genetic mutation which is capable of damaging DNA.

The implication of the above findings for policy is that effort should be made by critical stake holders such as the federal and state governments to come up with measures that will minimize if not eliminate the growing incidence of air pollution arising from illegal oil refining and unguarded release of

emissions by industries and oil installations. One such measure relates to the need for the federal government to strongly reposition the Department of Petroleum Resources (DPR) so that the Department can be up and doing in discharging its statutory function of enforcing compliance with rules, standards, regulations and proscription of the unwholesome activities of oil industry operators.

Conclusion

Air pollution is caused by any undesirable substance, which enters the atmosphere. The effective control measures of air pollution, and proper installation of air pollution control devices and their smooth functioning must be ensured before establishment of any industry. Emission from construction industries, and other human activities can be minimized by adopting best practices such as the use of water sprays for dust suppression, creating ridges to prevent dust, compaction of disturbed soil, prevention of dumping of earth materials along roadside etc. hence, restrictions may be imposed over the burning of waste product by both company and individual family. Thus, the effect of air pollution: Black soot and the damage potable domestic and rainwater have accounted for major air pollution issue for this study. However, findings have reviews that air pollution in Port Harcourt is as a result of industrial activities and illegal bunker activities in the area of Port Harcourt and has resulted to the shutdown of various economic and social activities in the city. Thus, the finding also shows that peoples in Port Harcourt have been affected in their business and social life and therefore perceive air pollution as a source of black soot in their various residence and business area.

Furthermore, it was recommended that Government should implement and monitors the compliance of industries and human activities on Air Pollution policies. Additionally, it was also recommended that Government should also encourage oil and gas companies to recycle and reuse their waste product for other production to the public in other to reduce air pollution effect in the environment. Finally proper policy and monitoring team show be put in place to check illegal bunkering and other theft activities resulting to black soot in most area of Port Harcourt especially the oil production and pile line area as well as other industrial activities.

Recommendations

1. Government should Implementing and monitor the compliance of industries and human activities in Port Harcourt LGA using air pollution policies
2. Government should also encourage oil and gas companies to recycle and reuse their waste product for other production to the public to reduce air pollution effect in the environment.
3. Government, communities and individual should discourage bush burning to help reduce air pollution in the environment.
4. Government should continue to monitor, destroys and damage illegal bunkering camps within the environment to help reduce air pollution issues in the area.
5. There should be strict restrictions on old polluting vehicles; government may subsidies or swap the vehicles for new ones to reduce air pollution in the city.

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